

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF RICE CULTIVATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya. Mamlakatimizda sifatli va raqobatbardosh oziq-ovqat maxsulotlarini yetishtirish, sarflanayotgan tabiiy va moddiy resurslardan, zamonaviy va tejamkor texnologiyalar yordamida samarali foydalanish, avvalo, mamlakat oziq-ovqat strategiyasi yo'nalishlari talablarini bajarish va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, boshqa tomondan, korxonalarining mavjud mehnat, yer, suv, moddiy va moliyaviy resurslaridan, mulk shakllaridan qat'iy nazar, ular o'rtasidagi iqtisodiy munosabatlarni takomillashtirish asosida, oqilona foydalanish evaziga tarmoq samaradorligini oshirish muhim hisoblanadi.

Аннотация. Выращивание в нашей стране качественной и конкурентоспособной продовольственной продукции, эффективное использование потребляемых природных и материальных ресурсов с помощью современных и рентабельных технологий, в первую очередь, служит выполнению требований направлений продовольственной стратегии страны и обеспечению продовольствием. безопасность. Также, с другой стороны, важно повысить эффективность работы сети за счет рационального использования имеющихся трудовых, земельных, водных, материальных и финансовых ресурсов предприятий, независимо от форм собственности, на основе совершенствования экономических отношений. между ними.

Abstract. Cultivation of high-quality and competitive food products in our country, effective use of consumed natural and material resources with the help of modern and cost-effective technologies, first of all, serves to fulfill the requirements of the country's food strategy directions and ensure food safety. Also, on the other hand, it is important to increase the efficiency of the network through the rational use of existing labor, land, water, material and financial resources of enterprises, regardless of the forms of ownership, based on the improvement of economic relations between them.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy samaradorlik, rentabellik, asosiy ko'rsatkichlar, tizim, foyda, moddiy xarajat, daromad, ekin maydoni, yalpi mahsulot, xosildorlik, sof foyda, moliyaviy mablag'lar.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность, рентабельность, основные показатели, система, преимущества, материальные затраты, доход, посевная площадь, валовой продукт, урожайность, чистая прибыль, финансовые фонды.

Keywords: economic efficiency, profitability, key indicators, system, profit, material cost, income, cultivated area, gross product, productivity, net profit, financial resources.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), global climate change and rapid population growth will further increase the need for food in most countries. is causing. Because the world's population will reach 9.2 billion people by 2050, it is necessary to increase the production of agricultural products by 70%. Also, the goal of the economic reforms implemented in the agriculture of our country is to satisfy the population's needs for food products in terms of quantity and quality. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Strengthening the health of our people, establishing a healthy lifestyle is a vitally important issue for us. I repeat, if we ensure peace and health, we will achieve everything else. The goal of agricultural reforms is to ensure food security and increase people's well-being, along with economic benefits.

At the same time, in the process of liberalization and modernization of the economy, the priority directions for increasing the production of food products today and in the future are "Growing of agricultural products, increasing exports, applying modern technologies to the sector, and paying special attention to the rational use of water resources." it is necessary to pay attention."

It is known that rice products are one of the main daily food products of the population of our republic. Therefore, during the reforms in the agrarian sector, a number of measures were implemented, paying special attention to rice production. In particular, the following legal-normative documents were accepted; Presidential Decree No. 4973 of February 2, 2021 "On Measures for the Further Development of Rice Cultivation", No. 986 of December 12, 2019 "On Additional Measures for the Sustainable Development of Rice Cultivation" Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 362 dated June 10, 2021 "On approval of the temporary regulation on the procedure for reimbursing part of the cost of modern seed drills and planting equipment purchased for rice planting", 2021 Cabinet of Ministers decision No. 381 dated June 18 "On approval of the

regulation on the procedure for selecting seed farms for the cultivation of seed rice belonging to the super-elite, elite and next generations" is one of them.

Rice is one of the most common cereal crops. Currently, it serves as the main food for more than two-thirds of the world's population. Rice plays such an important role in the culture, economy and food supply of many countries that their main policy is to produce enough of it to avoid dependence on very limited imports.

Rice is considered one of the food products that are part of the daily life needs of the people of our republic, and in recent years, the area of cultivated rice has been reduced and the productivity has decreased significantly. The decrease in the amount of rice production is caused by the shortage of irrigation works, the deterioration of the amelioration of arable land, the lack of introduction of a scientifically based system of specialization, the fact that the material-technical and innovation system in the sector is in an unsatisfactory state, as a result of the cancellation of the mechanism for the purchase of rice products for the state needs, rice raw materials causing certain problems in the economic relations between the growing farms and the processing enterprises.

Based on the above, the development of scientific proposals and practical recommendations aimed at solving the existing problems in the field of rice production of our republic is one of the urgent issues in the agrarian sector reforms.

High-quality and competitive agriculture in our republic, mainly the production of food products, the main directions, ideas and recommendations of effective use of natural and material resources with the help of modern and cost-effective technologies, decisions, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev, Scientific books and special literature are scientifically and practically based.

Z.F. Anikanova, S.A. Avezboev, SH. Bakirov, V.B. Zaitsev, N.T. Kogoy, A. Kadirov, A.M. Scientists such as Kadyrov, U.M. Mullajanov, A.V. Nesterov, A.Ramazanov, F.Rahimboev, R.Kh. Husanov, I.E. Rafikov, T.Kh. Farmonov, Q.A. Choriev conducted scientific research.

In particular, F.A. Baraev, O'.P. Umurzakov, A.G. Ibragimov's special scientific research work is dedicated to the development of new technologies of optimal reclamation system and irrigation for obtaining a high yield from rice.

At a time when there is a food shortage in many countries of the world, issues such as ensuring food security in our republic, including meeting the needs of the population for rice products, and developing the rice industry based on

scientific structural changes in the conditions of water shortage, are sufficiently addressed. the fact that it has not been researched determines the relevance of the research, which is the basis for choosing this work as a dissertation topic.

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